

PHIRUGU NANDI NAADI AND CINEMA FIELDS

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Abstract:

There are so many duties and jobs in cinema field. Film producer, Director, Actor, Hero, Script writer, Lyric writer, Music Director, Play back Singer, Cinematographer, Editor, Stunt Master, Dance master, Art director, Sound engineer, etc... According to phirugu nandi naadi there are some combinations for the above pepole.

Key Words: Phirugu Nandi Naadi, Cinema, Producer, Director, Actor, Hero Script Writer, Lyric Writer, Music Director, Play Back Singer, Cinematographer, Stunt Master, Dance Master, Art Director, Sound Engineer, Planet Combinations

Introduction:

Who will shine in which job is very important to us. Now a days most of the astrologers follow Phirugu Nandi Naadi to satisfy their customers. Learning and using this method is very easy and very accuracy.

PNN Rule for Film Producer:

Jupiter has conjunction with venus and Saturn in 1/5/9 or 3/7/11 or 2/12 position

Example Chart:

Producer AM. Rathnam - Sri Surya movies
 Ghilli, Indian, Mudhalvan, Kushi, Vedalam Movie maker

VENUS MARS	JUPITER		
	RASI CHART 04.02.1953		KETHU
MERCURY SUN RAHU			
		SATURN	MOON

In his horoscope Jupiter aspects Saturn and Saturn also aspects Jupiter. Jupiter and Venus are standing in 2/12 position. This makes him a famous film producer in Tamil, Telugu and Hindi.

PNN Rule for film Director:

Jupiter has conjunction with venus or Sun or Rahu in 1/5/9 or 3/7/11 or 2/12 position. This makes one a successful director.

Example Chart 1: Vijaya T. Rajhendar

		KETHU	
MARS	RASI CHART 09.05.1955		
			JUPITER VENUS
	RAHU SATURN		SUN MOON MERCURY

He is called "Astaavathaani". His movies Rayil payanangalil, Oruthalai ragam, Uyirullavarai usha, Thangaikor geetham, En Thangai Kalyani, Oru Thayin Sabatham, Mythili ennai kathali are very famous. In his horoscope Jupiter and venus conjunction in same sign. Jupiter and Sun stand in 2 / 12 position. This makes him an excellent director.

Example Chart 2: K. Bhagyaraj (Drum stick famous)
 Munthanai Mudichu, Chokka Thangam

JUPITER RAHU	RASI CHART 07.01.1953		
MARS VENUS			KETHU

SUN MOON MERCURY			SATURN
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In his horoscope Jupiter and Venus stand in 2 / 12 position Jupiter and Rahu in same sign Jupiter and Sun stand in 3/11 position.

PNN Rule for Film Heroes:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus a Sun or Rahu. This makes on a successful hero.

Ilaya Thilagam Prabhu:

MARS		KETHU	
	RASI CHART 25.12.1956		
MERCURY			
SUN MOON	RAHU VENUS SATURN		JUPITER

In his horoscope both Jupiter and Venus, Jupiter and Rahu have 3 /11 conjunction. So, as a son of Nadigar Thilagam Sivaji Ganesan, Prabhu has the successful place in Tamil film industry.

PNN Rule for Script Writer:

Jupiter, has conjunction with Venus or Moon or Mercury. This type of horoscope makes one a very good script writer

Actor, Director K. Bhagyaraj:

JUPITER RAHU	RASI CHART 07.01.1953		
MARS VENUS			KETHU
SUN MOON MERCURY			SATURN

In his horoscope Jupiter and Venus stand in 2/12 position. Jupiter with Moon and Mercury stand in 3/11 position. This gives great fame to K. Bhagyaraj as the best script writer.

PNN Rule for Lyric Writer:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus or Moon or Mercury. This type of horoscope makes one a very good lyric writer.

Kaviyarsar Kannadhasan:

JUPITER	MOON		SUN RAHU
	RASI CHART 24.06.1927		MERCURY VENUS MARS
KETHU	SATURN		SATURN

In his horoscope Jupiter conjunction with moon in 2/12 position. Moon is the planet for mood. It joins with Jupiter. So, he wrote evergreen songs.

PNN Rule for Stunt Master:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus or Mars makes one a great stunt master.

Stunt Master Kanal Kannan:

VENUS		MOON	
MARS SUN JUPITER MERCURY	RASI CHART 12.03.1962		RAHU
KETHU SATURN			

In his horoscope Jupiter and Mars stand in same house. Jupiter and Venus stand in 2/12 position. This makes him an excellent stunt master.

PNN Rule for Music Director:

Jupiter has conjunction with Sun or Venus or Rahu.

Maestro Ilayaraja M.P:

MARS		MOON SUN MERCURY SATURN	
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		VENUS JUPITER RAHU
KETHU	RASI CHART 02.02.1943	

In his horoscope Jupiter conjunctions with Venus and Rahu in same house with exhaltation Power. And also conjunctions with Sun in 3/11 position. They gives him name and fame.

PNN Rule for Play Back Singer:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus or Mercury makes one an excellent play back singer.

		SUN RAHU MERCURY	VENUS SATURN
	RASI CHART 04.06.1946		MOON MARS
	KEHTU		JUPITER

In his horoscope Jupiter conjunctions with mercury in 5/9 position trine very auspicious one. So, he achieves Guinness world record.

PNN Rule for Cinematographer:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus or Moon or Rahu makes one an excellent cinematographer.

P. C. Sriram:

		KETHU	MOON
VENUS	RASI CHART 26.01.1956		
MERCURY SUN			JUPITER
	SATURN MARS RAHU		

In his horoscope Jupiter and moon conjunction in 3/11 position. Jupiter aspects Venus and also Venus aspects Jupiter. So, he got the great place in Indian cinema field as the best cinematographer.

PNN Rule for Supportive Actor:

Jupiter has conjunction with Venus or Rahu or Sun makes one an excellent supportive actor.

Comedian Goundamani:

MERCURY SATURN SUN	KETHU		
JUPITER MOON	RASI CHART 18.03.1939		
VENUS			JUPITER
MARS		RAHU	

His horoscope Jupiter conjunction with Rahu in 5/9 position. Jupiter conjunctions with Venus in 2/12 position. Jupiter conjunctions with Sun in 2/12 position. It gives him a fame equal to the hero in tamil movies.

Conclusion:

We can easily attract our clients through Phirugu Nandi Naadi with accurate predictions No need lagna, no need dasa bukthi is the special one

References:

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